

Changing Cropping Pattern in Haryana: A Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Major Food Crops

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ABSTRACT

The cropping pattern of a crop determined by the number of factors in an area of production, and also determines the food habits of the local population. There are many changes take place in the cropping pattern of Haryana since the Green Revolution during the 1960s to dates. Wheat and rice are the major staple food crops of the Haryana state for which the green revolution was very successful. The present research article is attempted to present an analytical account of wheat and rice crops in the Haryana. Analysis reveals that the sown area and yield under wheat and rice suffer from temporal as well as a spatial variation over the reference period of the study i.e. 2001-2018 across the districts of Haryana. The Cropping pattern of Haryana highly affects by the green revolution because it enhance the production and price of wheat and rice which affects the mindset of the farmers. However, the present pattern of farming in the Haryana has completely been transformed from intensive farming to market-oriented forming of the crops for profit-making business. Extensive market-oriented agriculture farming in Haryana has affected the soil fertility, underground water table, nutritional value of crops and environment as well.

Keywords: Agriculture-System, Cropping Pattern, Fertility, Haryana, Spatio-Temporal.

INTRODUCTION

Cropping pattern means a share of land under separate crops at a point of time, differences occur in the present distribution and also the circumstances which affect cropping pattern over the period of time (Misra & Puri: 2011). Rice-wheat (RW) schemes are of great importance for food safety and livelihoods in South Asia (Humphreys and Roth, 2008). Rice and wheat are now frequently produced in double-cropping rotational pattern and its average yield highly varies from place to place. There is a need to be enlarged significantly to meet rising demands due to the growing population, urbanization and economic growth (Aggarwal, et al., 2000). A large number of farm trials were showed at farmers' fields in Haryana, to evaluate the performance of the mechanical transplanted rice (MTR) under non-puddled and no-till situations as compared to conventional puddled transplant rice (CPTR) (Baldev Raj Kamboj et al., 2013). The agriculture system of J&K was followed traditions of the region which fulfill only basic requirements. Green revolution makes a big difference in state agriculture, now farmers growing crops as according to market value and try to earn more and more profit (Singal, 2015). Haryana is a leading state of India in food grains and milk production. Almost 65-70 percent of the state's population engaged in agricultural activities. If we talking about irrigation, underground water is the main source of irrigation in the Haryana state and canal, other sources are in the second position.

The green revolution played a great role in agricultural development in Haryana and made it self-sufficient in food production. Haryana stands on the third rank in per capita income among all the states of our country. It holds sustainable growth in the field of agriculture and manufacturing from the 1970's and it is an economically developed region in South Asia (Misra And Puri, 2011). If we talking about the 1960-70s, almost all the crops were grown in Haryana, but after the green revolution in the field of agriculture, farmers would like to grow only two crops which were wheat and rice. So the cropping pattern of the state faces many changes. Farmers are focused only on profit, they do not care about the water level and soil fertility. This research paper is basically trying to interrogate that what changes have been occurred in cropping pattern of wheat and rice in Haryana since 2001 to 2018. In order to investigate the changing pattern of selected food crops, the research paper has focused on the two major objectives: 1) to analyze the cropping pattern of two major crops of Haryana during the last eighteen years and, 2) to give some suggestion to improve agriculture system in Haryana.

DATA SOURCE AND METHODOLOGY

The present study is a quantitative exercise-based on the secondary data primarily extracted from Agricultural Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018). Besides, different other sources like district statistical office, economic survey and government publications and report has been used to supplement our analysis. The data of net sown area and yield per hecter in kilograms of two major crops of wheat and rice has been extracted from Agricultural Statistical Abstract Haryana for the time periods of 2001 to 2018 in order to full the objective of the study. The annual temporal trend of net sown area in hectares and yield per hectares in kilograms of both the crops have been plotted on the separate bar diagraphs for 2001-2018. For analyzing the spatial pattern of wheat and rice crops, a district-wise choropleth map of the average net sown area and yield of five years for both crops has been plotted on the district wise map of Haryana. The map of the spatial distribution of the crops has been constructed by using the Geographical Information system technology. There isa total of 22 districts in Haryana at present. But we have used the map boundary of 19 districts of Haryana because there is no availability of old data of newly created districts in the States. Moreover, the absolute figures of the net sown area and yield per hectares for the crops have been used for analyzing the facts and figures in the study area.

The study area i.e. Haryana was formed as the 17th state of our country by the recommendation of Sardar Hukum Singh Parliamentary committee. Haryana state covered the area of 44212km² and 1.37% area covered in the country total and holds the rank of 22 in area percent. It is situated betwixt 27 degrees 37' to 30 degrees 55' North Latitude and 74 degrees 27' to 77 degrees 36' East Longitude. It was separated from Punjab in 1966 but both the states share the common capital UT Chandigarh. The total Population is 2.53 crore with 573 population density. Haryana is growing mainly two crops which are wheat and rice and it is on 3rd position in wheat production and 10th place in rice production at the country level. Haryana gets self-sufficiency in the 1970's in food grain production and holds the second position in the center pool of our country in food grains. Haryana is the biggest producer of two-wheeler, tractors, and cars. Haryana is divided into six administrative revenue divisions namely Ambala, Karnal, Rohtak, Gurugram, Faridabad, Hisar, and 22 districts. Haryana is a leading state in both agriculture and manufacturing but in the field of agriculture, it faces so many problems like low productivity, the small size of landholding, dark zones, soil degradation, focus on few crops, low yield and price of the crops which highly affects the cropping pattern in the state.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Figure 1 is showing the overall trend pattern of wheat production in the state of Haryana over a period of time 2100-2018. The figure indicates that there is a steady pace of annual production of wheat in kilograms per hectare and net sown area in hectares from 2001-02 to 2008-09. In 2009-10, both figures (yield & area) of wheat suddenly has increased from 4000 kg per hectare 4600 Kg per hectare.

Figure 1: Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Similarly, the Net sown area has also increased from 2460 to 2859 thousand hectares during the same period of time. After that annual yield and net sown area under wheat crops is showing a fluctuation between 4600 to 4800 kg of yield and 2859 to 2500 thousand hectares in the net sown area. Therefore, both yield and net sown area highlighted and reflect that the net sown area under wheat remains almost the same except the year 2009-2010. As the population is increasing day by day but the land is limited. If we talking about yield per hectare, it also reflects very few changes in positive growth in the year 2009-10,2012-13,2016-17 and 2017-18. Factors like the poor condition of farmers, poor infrastructure facilities, decreasing landholding size highly affects the production. Thus, is maybe called a steady pace of wheat production and net sown area for wheat farming with little exception over the reference period of time of the study.

Figure 2 displays the overall temporal pattern of rice production in Haryana from 2100 to 2018. Figures net sown area under rice production indicates that there is a slow increasing net sown area along with high fluctuation over the reference period of time. Similarly, yield per hectare in kg of rice crops is also showing fluctuation pace of slowly increasing over the reference period of the study. In the case of the net sown area, it fluctuates from 1054 thousand hectares in 2001-02 to 1385 thousand hectare hectares in 2017-18 for the net sown area.

Figure 2: Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Similarly, annual yield per hectare of wheat crops is showing a slow pace of increase with high fluctuation between 2557 to 3213 kg of yield over the reference period of the study. Likewise, the yield of rice also rose from 2557 kg per hectare in 2001-02 to 2017-18. Therefore, both the things i.e. net sown area and yield of rice crops have been increased over the period of reference of the study. Thus, it may be safe to say that the net sown area under rice is showing a positive growth almost in all the years except the 2003-04 and yield also increasing from 2001 to 2009. After 2009, the yield remains fluctuated up and down. Perhaps the yield of rice and wheat remains low as compared to other countries like the U.S.A., Philippines, etc. because of better farm technologies of these countries. Thus, is maybe called a slow pace of rice production and net sown area for rice farming with high fluctuation over the reference period of time of the study.

Regional Trend of Production of Wheat Crops

Figure 3: Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Figure 3 shows that the overall district wise pattern of the net sown area under wheat crops in the Haryana. It is suggested that the district Hisar is showing the largest net sown area under wheat crops with 250.0 to 300.0 thousand hectares during the reference period of the study from 2001-02-2017-18. The district of Sirsa, Jind and Jind are one of the largest net sowed areas under wheat crops during the reference period of the study. On the other hand, district Panchkula is registering the smallest net sown area under wheat crops (16 to 17 thousand hectares) preceded by Mahendragarh, Rewari and Yamuna Nagar over the reference period of time of the study.

Figure 4: Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Figure 4 showing a general pattern of yield per hectare for wheat crops at district levels in the Haryana. It is advocated that the district Gurgaon has started increasing the productivity of wheat from 2006-07 and highest (9359 kg per hectare.) was in 2012-13 and again it decreased at a very low level in 2017-18. Similarly, the productivity of wheat also suddenly increased in 2008-09 and it was highest (9904 kg per hectare.) in 2012—13. And was (9078 kg) in 2017-18. On the other

hand, district Panchkula is showing the lowest yield per hectare over the reference period of the study. Thus, it may say that the yield of all districts remains the same or a little up and down. Faridabad was in 1st place with the highest yield of 9078kg. /hectares, followed by Gurgaon with 8834kg/hectare and Bhiwani were on 3rd place in yield of 8642kg/hectare which was double according to last year yield.

Figure 5 displays that overall district wise pattern of the net sown area under rice crops during 2001-02-2017-18 in Haryana. The figures tell that the district Karnal is recording the largest net sown area under rice crops with 158.0 to 174.0 thousand hectares during the reference period 2001-02-2017-18. The district Karnal is followed by Kaithal, Kurukshetra and Jind in the largest net sown area under rice crops during the reference period. On the other hand, district Rewariis registering the smallest net sown area under Rice crops preceded by Panchkula Gurgaon and Bhiwani over the reference period of time of the study.

Figure 5: Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Thus, it may say that the net sown area under rice is remains high in Karnal district from 2001 to 2018 and followed by Kaithal. Kurukshetra remained on the third position in a net sown area with few ups and downs. Jind district also shows a huge up and down in the net sown area under rice. Overall district wise pattern of the net sown area under rice crops are varying district to district annually over the period of time of the referenced year.

Figure 6 shows the general district wise pattern of yield per hectare for rice crops during 2001-02-2017-18 in the state of Haryana. The yield of rice production shows that the district Gurgaon is recording the highest yield per hectare for rice crops with 5142 Kg in 2007-08 to 4739 kg in 2017-18 during the reference period. Similarly, district Faridabad also recording the second-highest rice yield after Gurgaon followed Fatehabad and Kurukshetra in rice crops during the reference period. On the other hand, district Rohtak is registering the smallest net sown area under Rice crops preceded by Jhajjar, Bhiwani, and Hisar respectively during the reference period of the study.

Figure 6: Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

In Nutshell, district Gurgaon was on 1st place in highest yield and Faridabad was on 2nd place in yield per hectare. They occupy 1st and 2nd positions because of the combined yield of both the district with Nun & Palwal. If we talking about separately, Fatehabad and Kurkshetra have on 1st and 2nd place in yield of rice. There is no rice production in Mahendragarh. Overall district wise pattern of the yield of rice crops are varying district to district annually over the period of time of the referenced year.

SPATIAL PATTERN OF PRODUCTION OF RICE CROPS

Map 1 is showing the average net sown area for 2001-02 to 2005-06 (five-year average) under rice crops that only 2 districts namely Karnal and Kaithal are registering average largest net sown area for rice crops in the Haryana. There are two districting namely Kurkshetra and Jind is recording medium average of net sown area for rice production. However, the largest numbers of districts such as 13 Sirsa, Hisar; Bhiwani Meat, etc. are showing a smaller net sown area of rice crops in Haryana state. Nonetheless, district Mahendragarh has no production of rice in the state.

A similar pattern of average net sown area for 2006-07 to 2010-11 (five year average) under rice crops also showing in map 2 which indicates there is no change in the pattern of the net sown area under rice crops during the transformation from 2001-2006 to 2006-2011 (map-2).

Transformation of the average net sown area under rice production from 2006-11 to -2012-16 (from map-2 to Map-3) shows that two new districts from low average net sown area i.e. Sirsa and Sonipat have upgraded into a medium average of net sown area. Remaining districts are still holding a similar position as they were in the earlier year of rice production. In other words, there are three districts namely Karnal and Kaithal records largest average net sown area of rice production, 4 districts Kurukshetra, Jind, Sonipat and Fatehabad records medium size of average net sown area; and 12 districts like Sirsa, Bhiwani, and Yamuna Nagar, etc. are still showing low average net sown area for rice production.

The district Jind records changes in their status of the net sown area under rice crops from 2012-16 (map-3) to 2017-18 (map-4). Jind district has upgraded from (2012-16) medium size to the largest size of the net sown area under rice crops in 201-18. Remaining districts are having a similar position as they were in the session of 2012-16. In other words, there are three districts i.e. Jind, Karnal and Kaithal records largest average net sown area for rice crops, 4 districts Sirsa, Kurukshetra, Sonipat, and Fatehabad records medium size of average net sown area; and 11 districts like Panipat, Bhiwani, and Yamuna Nagar, etc. are still showing low average net sown area for rice production.

Map-1

Map-2

Map-3

Map-4

Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Overall, most of the (> 11 districts) districts records low average size of the net sown area for rice crop production during the reference period of the study. Since rice is a water consumable crop and in Haryana, most of the agriculture depends on the underground water source and that's why the area under rice is less than wheat.

The average per hectare yield of rice crop production during 2001-02 to 2005-06 (5 years) (Map-5) shows that 9 districts namely Sirsa, Ambala, and Fatehabad, etc. records high average yield of rice production and 7 districts like Jind, Sonipat, Hisar, etc. records medium level average yield. There are only 2 districts namely Jhajhar and Gurgaon record low-level yield of rice production in Haryana.

Similarly, the average yield of rice crops during 2006-07 to 2010-11 (5 years) (Map-6) suggest that 4 districts i.e. Gurgaon, Faridabad, Fatehabad, and Kurukshetra have recorded high average yield of rice production and 10 districts like Jind, Sirsa, and Yamuna Nagar, etc. records medium level average yield. Moreover, 4 districts namely Sonipat, Rohtak, and Jhajhar record low-level yield of rice production in Haryana. The change from 2001-02-2005-06 to 2006-07-2010-11 in an average yield of rice has been recorded that 9 districts of high yield reduced to 4 districts, and the remaining 5 districts declined to the medium level yield of rice production. Now, 7 districts producing medium yield during 2001-02-2005-06 has increased to 10 districts in 2006-07-2010-11. Finally, the number of low yield of rice has also increased from 2 districts into 4 districts i.e. Sonipat and Bhiwani declined their status from medium to low-level yield of rice. Thus, it is cleared that the number of districts of the higher-level yield of rice production has declined their status. Thus, there is a degradation of the yield of rice production during this period in Haryana.

The average yield of rice crops during 2011-12 to -2015-16 (5 years) (Map-7) shows that 2 districts i.e. Gurgaon and Faridabad record-high average yield of rice production and 7 districts like Ambala, Sirsa, and Fatehabad, etc. records medium level average yield.

Map-5

Map-6

Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Furthermore, 8 districts namely Hisar, Sonipat, and Rohtak record low-level yield of rice production. From map-6 to map-7 indicates that the number of districts has declined their status across the state. The change from 2006-07 to 2010-11 in the average yield of rice has been recorded that 4 districts of high yield reduced to 2 districts, and the remaining 2 districts dropped their status to the medium level yield of rice production. Moreover, 10 districts producing medium yield during 2006-07-2010-11 have decreased to 7 districts in 2011-12-2015-16. Finally, the number of low yield of rice has also increased from 4 districts into 8 districts declined their status from medium to low-level yield of rice production. Thus, it is noted that the number of districts of the higher level yield of rice production has declined their status across, especially to the low level yield of rice production i.e. very depressive picture of the state. 2011-12-2015-16

The average yield of rice production during 2016-17 to 2017-18 (5 years) (Map-8) shows that 3 districts i.e. Fatehabad, Gurgaon, and Faridabad record-high average yield of rice production and 7 districts like Ambala, Sirsa and Kurukshetra etc. records medium level average yield. Moreover, 8 districts namely Jind, Hisar, and Bhiwani registers low-level yield of rice production. The change from 2011-12-2015-16 to 2016-17-2017-18 in the average yield of rice has registered that 2 districts of high yield increased into 3 districts of the high level yield of rice production. However, 7 districts producing medium yield and 8 districts of the low level yield of rice production during 2011-12-2015-16 (map-7) remained unchanged their statuses in yield of rice production in 2016-17-2017-18 (map-8). Thus, it is noted that the number of districts of the higher level yield of rice production has not much declined their statuses. However, some of the districts have recorded positive or negative changes during this period of time.

SPATIAL PATTERN OF PRODUCTION OF WHEAT CROPS

The average net sown area under wheat crops for 2001-02 to 2005-06 (map-9) (five-year average) showing that only 3 districts namely Sirsa, Hisar and Jind records average largest net sown area for wheat crops production in Haryana. There are 6 districts namely Fatehabad, Bhiwani, Sonipat, etc. are showing the medium average of net sown area for wheat crops rice production. Moreover, 6 districts such as Jhajar, Gurgaon, Rohtak, etc. are showing a small net sown area and, 4 districts like Mahendragarh, Rewari, Yamuna Nagar, etc. Records very small net sown area under wheat crop production in Haryana. The pattern of average net sown area for 2006-07 to 2010-11 (5 year) under wheat crops showing that only 2 districts namely Sirsa and Hisar records average largest net sown area for wheat crops production; and 4 district namely

Fatehabad, Jind, Karnal etc. registering medium average of net sown area for wheat crops rice production. Furthermore, 9 districts such as Jhajhar, Gurgaon, Bhiwani, etc. records small net sown areas and, 4 districts like Mahendragarh, Rewari, and Yamuna Nagar, etc. are showing the very small net sown area under wheat crops rice production in the Haryana.

The change in the statuses of districts from 2001-2006 (map-9) to 2006-2011 (map-10) shows that district Jind has declined from high to the medium level average net sown area under wheat production in 2006-11 and become only 2 districts in the high average net sown area. Further 2 districts i.e. Bhiwani and Sonipat of medium net sown area of 2001-02-2005-06 have declined their status to the small net sown area under wheat crop production in 2006-07-2010-11 (Map-10). Total three districts i.e. Bhiwani, Sonipat and Faridabad of medium net sown area (map-9) have declined their statuses to the small net sown area under wheat crop production. None of the changes have been recorded in the statuses of 4 districts having a very small net sown area for wheat crop production.

The average net sown area for 2011-12 to 2015-16 (5 years) under wheat crops showing that there is no change has been recorded in the status of high average net sown area of 2 districts in 2011-12-2015-16. There 5 districts i.e. Jind, Karnal, Fatehabad, etc. showing the medium level net sown area under wheat crop production.

Map-9

Map-10

Map-11

Map-12

Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

Among these five districts, Hisar of small net sown area (map-9) has raised to the medium net sown area (map-10) in 2011-12-2015-16. There are 9 districts i.e. Hisar, Gurgaon Jhajhar, etc. of low net sown area in 2006-07-2010-11 have reduced in 7 districts in 2011-12-2015-16.

Among these 9 districts, Hisar rose to medium and Panipat declined to the very low net sown area in the state. There are 5 districts showing the very low net sown area under wheat crop production in 2011-12-2015-16. Among these five districts, Panipat (map-10) of 2006-07-2010-11) has declined to the very low net sown area of wheat production in 2011-12-2015-16 (Map-11). Overall, the number of districts has declined from their higher status to lower status (map-10 to map-11).

Map-12 display that pattern of average net sown area under wheat crops for 2016-17 to 2017-18 (5 years) showing that only 1 district Sirsa records average largest net sown area under wheat crops and; 6 districts like Kaithal, Jind, and Karnal, etc. recording medium net sown area under wheat crops in Haryana. Total 7 districts i.e. Fatehabad, Bhiwani, and Sonipat, etc. are showing the small net sown area under wheat crop production. Similarly, there is 5 districts Mahendragarh, Rewari, Yamuna Nagar, etc. records a very small net sown area under wheat crop production. The average net sown area under wheat production for 2016-17-2017-18 (map-12) shows that only one district of Sirsa records a high average net sown area. The district Hisar of the higher net sown area has declined into the medium level net sown area in 2016-17-2017-18 (map-12). Though there is no change in a number of districts under small net sown area wheat production Yamuna Nagar's status rose up to the low net sown area in this group. Moreover, district Ambala of the low net sown area has gone down into the very low net sown area under wheat crops. There is no change in the number of districts of the very low net sown area but Yamuna Nagar rose to low and Ambala of Low to the very low net sown area under wheat crop production. Overall, no much change in statuses of districts has recorded in 2016-17-2017-18 (map-11 & map-12).

Map-13

Map-14

Map-15

Map-16

Source: Statistical Abstract Haryana (2001-2018)

The average yield of wheat production for 2001-02 to 2005-06 (map-13) (5 years) showing that only one district i.e. Sirsa records average high yield of wheat production. The medium yield of wheat production records by 6 districts namely Fatehabad, Jind, and Kamal, etc. Furthermore, 5 districts such as Hisar, Sonipat, and Mahendragarh, etc. are showing a low yield of wheat production. There are 7 districts such as Bhiwani, Gurgaon, Rohtak, etc. are showing a very low yield of wheat production in the Haryana (map-13).

The changing pattern of the yield of wheat from 2001-2-2005-06 (map-13) to 2006-07-2010-11 (map-14) shows that 3 district records high yield, 7 districts medium yield, 7 districts low yield, and 2 districts very low yield of wheat production in Haryana. District Faridabad and Rewari have risen from low yield to high yield and Gurgaon from very low to high yield. While Sirsa has gone down from high to medium yield, so 6 districts became 7 in the medium yield of wheat production. Among the 7 districts of low yield category, Bhiwani, Rohtak, Jhajjar, Yamuna Nagar, and Ambala have risen from very low to low yield of wheat production. Among 2 districts of very low, Jind has declined from medium to very low yield of wheat production. Overall most of the districts have raised their statuses from low to a higher category of yield in wheat production during 2001-2-2005-06 (map-13) to 2006-07-2010-11 (2014).

The changing pattern of the yield of wheat production from 2010-11 (map-14) to 2015-16 (map-15) shows that 2 district records high yield, 6 districts medium yield, 6 districts low yield, and 5 districts very low yield of wheat production in Haryana (map-15). Among the 6 medium yields, district Rewari has gone down from high yield to medium yield wheat production. Among the 6 districts of low yield, Sonipat and Panipat have declined from medium to low yield of wheat production. Moreover, among 5 districts of very low yield, Rewari, Jhajjar, Bhiwani, Rohtak have declined from low yield category to very low yield category in 2015-16 (map-15). Overall several districts have degraded their status from higher to lower yield category during 2010-11 (map-14) to 2015-16 (map-15).

The changing pattern of the yield of wheat production from 2016-17 (map-15)-2017-18 (map-18) suggests that 2 districts i.e. Gurgaon and Faridabad have remained in high yield of wheat production. There is only one district Bhiwani in medium yield which has arisen from very low yield to medium yield of wheat production. Total 3 districts i.e. Fatehabad, Sirsa, and Karnal have recorded low yield of wheat production. These three district have declined their status from medium yield to low yield of wheat production. The largest number of districts i.e. 10 out of 19 have recorded very low yield of wheat production. Most of these districts have declined from higher yield to lower yield of wheat production. Thus, it is noted that the majority of the districts have lowered their status of the yield of wheat production in Haryana.

DISCUSSION

Temporal analysis of the yield of wheat production reveals that a steady pace of the yield of wheat production and net sown area for under wheat farming with little exception over the reference period from 2001-02 to 2017-18. The temporal pattern of net sown area of rice production shows that a slow pace of rice production and the net sown area has been recorded for rice farming with high fluctuation over the reference period of the study.

District wise temporal pattern indicates that Hisar has the largest and Panchkula smallest net sown area under wheat crops during 2001-02-2017-18. However, most of the districts remain steady with little fluctuation in the net sown area under wheat crops during 2001-02-2017-18. The yield of wheat production in all the districts remains almost steady pace during the reference period. However, Faridabad and Gurgaon record the largest and Panchkula smallest net sown area under wheat production during the reference period.

Similarly, the net sown area under rice crops reveals that Karnal records the largest and Rewari smallest net sown area under rice crops during the reference period. Generally, district wise patterns of net sown area under rice crops are varying district to district annually over the reference period. In case of the yield of rice production, district Gurgaon records the highest yield and Rohtak lowest yield of rice production over the reference period of 2001-02 to 2017-18. Normally, the yield of rice crops is varying from one district to another district during the study period.

The spatial pattern of average net sown under rice production indicates that Karnal and Kaithal record the largest average net sown area under rice crops. On the contrary, the majority of the district (13 districts) comes under the smallest net sown area under rice crop production in 2001-02-2005-06 (map-1). There is no change recorded in 2006-07-2010-11. All the districts are showing a similar pattern of the net sown area under rice crops in 2006-07-2010-11 also (map-2). During 2006-11 -2012-16, only two districts from the low net sown area have risen into the medium net sown area for rice production. However, most of them (12 districts) districts record low average size of the net sown area for rice crop production (map-3). Three districts show the larger net sown area under rice production, while most of the (> 11 districts) districts records

low average size of the net sown area for rice crop production in 2016-17-2017-18.

Analysis reveals that a total of 9 districts show high yield and only 2 districts show a very low yield of rice production in 2001-02-2005-06 (map-5). Moreover, the majority of the districts declined their position in yield of rice production in 2006-07-2010-11 (map-6). Similarly, a number of districts of higher yield of rice production have also declined their status in 2011-12-2015-16 (map-7). Again most of the districts have remained the same with little up gradation along with few districts recorded change during this period (map-8).

The spatial pattern of net sown area under wheat production reveals that three districts of the medium area have declined their statuses to a small area under. Remaining districts show no changes in 2006-07-2010-11 (map-10). There is only one district upgraded in 2011-12-2015-16 (map-11). Remaining most of the districts do not records change their status (map-11). There is no much change in statuses of districts has recorded except few in 2016-17-2017-18 (map-12) in the net sown area under wheat production.

The spatial analysis of yield wheat production indicates that the majority of the districts have raised their statuses from lower to a higher category of the yield of wheat production in 2006-07-2010-11 (map-14). Number districts have degraded their status from higher to lower yield categories in 2011-12-2015-16 (map-15). Likewise, the majority of the districts have lowered their status of the yield of wheat production in Haryana in 2016-17-2017-18 (map-18).

CONCLUSION

Haryana is one of the largest food grains producing a state in India. The cropping pattern of Haryana was highly influenced by the green revolution for the production of food grains. Haryana was one of the most successful states in the green revolution for the production of wheat and rice. However, the analysis of the net sown area under wheat and rice crops along with yield of both crops indicates that there was temporal variation in the sown area and yield of both the crops over the reference period of the study. Moreover, net sown area and yield of wheat and rice production suffers from spatial variation over the reference period of the study i.e. 2001-2018 across the districts of Haryana. The Cropping pattern of Haryana highly affects by the green revolution because it enhances the production and price of wheat and rice which affects the mindset of the farmers. They want more profit by growing only two crops which affect the traditional cropping pattern of Haryana. The high production of wheat and rice in Haryana due to the green effect of the green revolution in Haryana has the impact of consistently environmental degradation, particularly of soil, vegetation, and water resources. Soil organic matter levels are declining and the use of chemical inputs is intensifying (Singh (2010). Due to the excess cultivation of rice in water deficit districts, it would raise problems like dark zones. To take Crop diversification in agriculture is a must in Haryana. The government should take incentives to spread awareness among the farmers about the benefits of growing different crops (Singral, 2015). Farmers should aware of their soil and water condition and then grow crops which suits in these conditions. Try to enhance bio-farming and less water consumable crops.

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